

YOU WILL GIVE IN PAIN: OBSTETRIC VIOLENCE AS AN EXPRESSION OF WOMAN'S BODY CONTROL

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8025676

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ABSTRACT

The control of women's bodies was placed as a central strategy of capitalism, reducing them to a privileged place for the implementation of techniques of power and power relations. In view of this, the present work aims to discuss obstetric violence as an expression of control of the woman's body. To this end, we resorted to bibliographical and documentary research, using the category of gender violence as a reference, anchored in historical-dialectical materialism. It is concluded that obstetric violence will occur during prenatal, delivery and postpartum care, including abortion, through the routine use of technology, medicalization and the idea of pathologizing pregnancy, annihilating the autonomy and women's decision-making capacity. However, there is no federal or specific legislation in Brazil that conceptualizes it and provides for sanctions for those who practice it (leaving victims with a great feeling of powerlessness and impunity), added to incipient public policies and the silencing of the term "obstetric violence" (which prevents the real dimension of the issue). limit of the destructive action of capital, contradictions that are part of the nature of a society of classes.

Keywords: Obstetric Violence. Patriarchy. Body Control.

INTRODUCTION

Obstetric violence is characterized as gender violence, and is therefore committed against women in all stages of pregnancy and postpartum, including cases of abortion, as a hidden face of the moral regime of control of bodies by gender, inserted within the productive process, medicated and contained. A process that implies the violation of human, sexual and

reproductive rights, and the loss of women's autonomy, undermining their protagonism by being subjugated.

This is a problem that is very present in Brazilian health services, but silenced as "natural labor pain", insofar as the experience is relativized and discredited by the doctor's words, based on the power of ideology, power over life and in the power of the androcentric and misogynistic order.

Contradictorily (or not), there is no federal legislation that typifies "obstetric violence", a term silenced by the Ministry of Health, which in 2019 issued an opinion, claiming that its use impairs humanized care, does not add value and has an inadequate connotation. Perspective that ignores the reality experienced by the victims and is structured in social relations of sex, class, race/ethnicity, which embody capitalist society - since its incidence is even greater among black and poor women. Perversely rebounding also on women in situations of abortion and post-abortion, victims of moralizing behaviors, which criminalize and deny the right to abortion.

It is recognized here that transgender men can become pregnant and experience violent obstetric situations, but we will refer to the term "woman", referring to cisgender women, the majority target of this type of violence. In view of this, the objective of this work is to situate obstetric violence as an expression of body control, a primordial understanding in the struggle for rights in the fight against multiple forms of violence against women. Rights that should not be seen as an end in itself, but inserted within the limits of a society that has inequality and exploitation as constituents.

DOCILIZATION OF THE WOMAN'S BODY IN CAPITALISM

Engels (1997) already clarified that the subordination of women to male oppression is characteristic of social relations initiated from the emergence of private ownership of the means of production. In the primitive communities, constituted by small migratory bands, in which they developed activities of gathering food available in nature, predominated:

[...] the division of labor [...] absolutely spontaneous; it only exists between the two sexes. Man goes to war, hunts and fishes, looks for raw materials for food, produces the necessary instruments to achieve his ends. The woman takes care of the house, prepares food and makes clothes, cooks, spins and sews. Each one commands his domain, the man in the forest and the woman in the house. Each one is the owner of the instruments that he elaborates and

uses; the man owns the weapons and hunting and fishing gear, the woman owns the household utensils. (p.178-179)

In this social formation, the sexual division of labor cannot be explained by the greater physical strength of men, since there were women who practiced hunting and gathering; the most convincing hypothesis was the need to breastfeed the baby, since “it is assumed that women were assigned the task of hunting. The slightest whisper of the baby would scare the animal destined for death and the hunters would invariably return to their group, without any food” (SAFFIOTI, 2015, p.64).

Although they did not hold greater power, women “were considered powerful, strong beings, true magical beings, by virtue of conceiving and giving birth, presumably alone” (idem, p.62), so that motherhood was never *an* element justification for submission, fragility and exclusion.

With the development of control over nature, enabling the formation of surplus production, and the discovery of the indispensability of man to engender a new life, he can assume control over women. Patriarchy would emerge, transforming “the existing affective bonds between men and women, between mothers and children and between women among themselves in power relations” (MURARO, 1995, p.64) as a social and sexual pact, which establishes the systematic access of men to the female body, representing a power structure based on both ideology and violence (SAFFIOTI, 2015).

Federici (2017), then, understands that the control of female bodies was placed as a central strategy to build capitalism, which justifies and mystifies the contradictions embedded in its relationships, defaming the nature of those it exploits, among them the women who began to having your body seen as a privileged place for the implementation of techniques and power relations.

In capitalist society, the body is for women what the factory is for male wage workers: the main terrain of their exploitation and resistance, to the same extent that the female body has been appropriated by the state and by men, forced to function as means for reproduction and accumulation of work. In this sense, the importance acquired by the body in all its aspects - motherhood, childbirth and sexuality - both within feminist theory and in women's history, is well deserved. (FEDERICI, 2017, p.34)

The phenomenon of the "witch hunt" in Europe and the New World, reproduced in contemporary times, clearly demonstrates how control of women's bodies was claimed by society. They had their autonomy, prevalent in communities around the world, kidnapped, and therefore "witch hunt" cultural, political, ideological and economic determinant process that

helped in the production of surplus, presenting specific cuts in Latin America, in which the black, native and poor population played a central role.

appear , creating, initially, the linking of the figure of the heretic to the woman (the witch), so that the movements of heretics offered alternative approaches to sexuality and playback:

It is conceivable that in the sexual and reproductive codes of the heretics we can actually see remnants of a medieval attempt at birth control. This would explain why, when population growth became a fundamental social concern during the deep demographic crisis and with the shortage of workers in the 16th century, heresy came to be associated with reproductive crimes, especially 'sodomy', with infanticide and abortion (FEDERICI, 2017, p.79)

Crystallizing the transition to capitalism, the State becomes the manager of class relations, reproduction and the workforce, intervening in women's bodies by supervising sexuality, procreation and family life. More severe penalties would be imposed on contraception, infanticide and abortion, transforming women's bodies into instruments for reproduction and expansion of the workforce. Wombs were transformed into political territory, controlled by men and by the State, as a direct response to economic interests.

The State and the Catholic Church of the period imposed these measures because they understood that sexual desire gave women a certain power over men, representing a threat, making sexuality an object of shame, "a matter of State" (FEDERICI, 2017) . Consequently, throughout the 16th and 17th centuries, through the new sexual division of labor, women lost space in all dimensions of social life.

The public domain became destined for the masculine, while the women's space was marginalized to the private domain of the home and reproduction. That is, “the woman, in addition to being dominated, was reduced, along with sexuality, to a commodity or object of desire that promotes other commodities” (SUNG; SILVA, 1995, p.104-105), having her body transformed into the property of the her husband for her enjoyment and for the procreation of children (labor power), that is,

an heir who can perpetuate the accumulation of family wealth. This, in turn, has its status in society from the property it owns. The guarantee that the child will really belong to the husband is the wife's virginity – that's why the inheritance belongs to the firstborn male. Virginity becomes essential for the woman destined to be a wife, with which the development of her sexuality is compromised by repression (LESSA, 2012, p.31)

With the patriarchal and monogamous family, the home lost its social character and became a private service – turning the woman into the first servant, since the modern family is

based on disguised domestic slavery (ENGELS, 1997). Everything related to the domestic sphere emptied itself of the politicized that it enjoyed in communal life, which was due to the construction of new cultural canons, accentuating the differences between men and women, the latter being seen as inferior to men, demanding their control (FEDERICI, 2017).

Consequently, with the witch hunt, midwives lost space, occupied by male midwives and, later, by obstetric medicine. Childbirth, which was a practice of women, with women and for women, was attributed to men's knowledge and the development of obstetric medicine, making their bodies the target of the routine use of technology and medicalization, that is, "the entire set of of obstetric procedures is similarly reflected in the degradation of the woman's role in childbirth" (ODENT, 2002, p.12). Like this,

Wherever we looked, birth was being "medicalized", more technological [...] obstetrics focuses on the role of the doctor and his concern about the best way to perform and have control over childbirth. [...] they don't know and are even less concerned about the fact that labor, childbirth and the initial phase of breastfeeding are an integral part of a woman's sexual life (ODENT, 2002, p.17-18) .

Martin (2006) demonstrates how women's bodies were placed as a machine, productive process, complex and ideological that emerged throughout capitalist development. In view of this, the medical order does not recognize the role of women in childbirth, focusing on the result: the baby, the "merchandise", put into the world through the instruments and techniques of medicine and surrounded by the logic of productivity, amidst the value monetary value of health services and the commodified, fetishistic and alienated ideology.

In the face of inadequate and naturalized medical conduct (and that of other professionals involved in care), women are forced to overcome their own difficulties by annihilating their autonomy and decision-making capacity over their bodies. Being, therefore, strongly marked by a society that insists on controlling the body and sexuality of women, especially black and poor women, who suffer most from violence, when the understanding is disseminated that non-white women are strong and better able to bear pain:

It is not a question of adding racism + gender + social class, but of perceiving the new and composite reality that results from this fusion [...] a person is not discriminated against for being a woman, worker and black. Effectively, a woman is not doubly discriminated against, because, in addition to being a woman, she is also a salaried worker. Or, still, it is not triply discriminated against. These are not variables, but determinations, qualities, which make the situation much more complex (SAFFIOTI, 2015, p.115)

Gender, race and class, as categories of oppression, structure Brazilian society and permeate other forms of differentiation, constituting the core of violence perpetrated against women. Therefore, it is essential to understand when difference results in inequality and is the basis for building power, that is, universalizing violence against women, ignoring institutional and social class racism, is giving in to abstract rationality.

OBSTETRIC VIOLENCE: THE VITALITY OF PATRIARCHY IN CHILDBIRTH

Violence that impacts the body never encounters a dematerialized body, but one constituted by sex and sociability, since it is inscribed in a specific community and culture. Thus, violence is a worldwide, historical and multifaceted phenomenon. According to Minayo (2006):

Violence is not one, it is multiple. Of Latin origin, the word comes from the word *vis* which means strength and refers to the notions of constraint and the use of physical superiority over the other. In its material sense, the term seems neutral, but whoever analyzes violent events discovers that they refer to conflicts of authority, struggles for power and the will to dominate, to possess the annihilation of the other and his property. Its manifestations are approved or disapproved, licit or illicit according to social norms maintained by naturalized uses and customs or by legal apparatuses of society. Mutant, violence therefore designates - according to times, places and circumstances - very different realities. There is tolerated violence and there is condemned violence (p.13)

Reducing it to a fixed definition causes a misunderstanding of its evolution and historical specificity, in such a way that the author justifies the difficulty of its definition by being a “being a phenomenon of the order of the lived, whose manifestations provoke or are provoked by a strong emotional charge of those who commit it, those who suffer it and those who witness it” (p.14). Thus, violence cannot be analyzed outside the society that produces it, in this case, capitalist society.

That said, the Inter-American Convention to Prevent, Punish, and Eradicate Violence against Women defines violence against women as "any gender-based act or conduct that causes death, harm, or physical, sexual, or psychological suffering to women, whether public as well as in the private sphere. Gender comes from cultural and social differences, so that Saffioti (2001) defines gender violence as a broad concept arising from gender inequality that falls on women, subjecting them to the dictates of the patriarch and possible violence, capable of shaping behavior.

Based on this understanding, there is obstetric violence committed with a gender bias, explaining “the execution of the project of domination-exploitation of the social category men requires that their ability to command be aided by violence” (SAFFIOTI, 2001, p.115) and referring to the relationship between the “male” or those who occupy their place of power in patriarchal society and the social categories that are the target of their aggression (women, children and adolescents of both sexes).

There is a form of rape recognized by the World Health Organization in 2014 as a public health issue, revealing the withdrawal of the protagonism and objectification of women during the pregnancy-puerperal cycle, by having their body transformed into an object of intervention, something to be taken, contained and corrected. Therefore, it is defined as:

that which is committed against pregnant women in health services during prenatal care, delivery and postpartum, cesarean section and abortion. It can be verbal, physical, psychological or even sexual and it is expressed in different ways, sometimes explicit or hidden. Like other forms of violence against women, obstetric violence is strongly permeated by gender prejudices (VASCONCELOS; FORMIGA, 2016, p. 6)

It is a concept that gives visibility to violations permeated by stigmas and permeated by other types of violence, which health systems tolerate, or worse, reproduce and promote. This fact is reinforced by the incipient Brazilian scientific and legislative production on the subject, where the Venezuelan Legislation is appropriate, which in its Organic Law on the Right of Women to a Life Free from Violence, enacted in 2007, brought a critical concept of obstetric violence, understood as :

The appropriation of women's bodies and reproductive processes by health professionals, which is expressed in a dehumanized hierarchical treatment, in an abuse of medicalization and pathologization of natural processes, bringing with it a loss of autonomy and ability to decide freely about their bodies and their sexuality, negatively impacting the quality of life of women (VENEZUELA, 2007)

Despite seeming to be a sporadic problem, according to a survey by the Perseu de Abramo Foundation and Social Service of Commerce (SESC), in 2010, one in four women suffers some type of violence during childbirth, of which 65.9% are black. Here is a silenced and naturalized violence, since the treatments performed seem to help childbirth, hiding the professional's intention to speed up stages, no matter how interventionist it may be (PARTO DO PRINCIPIO, 2012).

It should be noted that obstetric violence is restricted to medical practice, and any professional participates in the care of women, covering “all those acts committed against

women in the exercise of their sexual and reproductive health” (PARTO DO PRINCIPIO, 2012, p. 60), in addition to the structural failures of the health system as a whole. Being, therefore, surrounded by characterizing acts, namely:

Physical character: actions that affect the woman's body, that interfere, cause pain or physical damage (from mild to severe), without a recommendation based on scientific evidence. [...] Psychological character: any verbal or behavioral action that causes feelings of inferiority, vulnerability, abandonment, emotional instability, fear, harassment, insecurity, deterrence, deception, alienation, loss of integrity, dignity and prestige in women. [...] Sexual character: any action imposed on women that violates their intimacy or modesty, affecting their sense of sexual and reproductive integrity, whether or not they have access to the sexual organs and intimate parts of their bodies. [...] Institutional character: actions or forms of organization that hinder, delay or prevent women's access to their constituted rights, whether these actions or services, of a public or private nature. [...] Material character: active and passive actions and conduct with the aim of obtaining financial resources from women in reproductive processes, violating their rights already guaranteed by law, for the benefit of an individual or legal entity. [...] Media character: actions carried out by professionals through the media, aimed at psychologically violating women in reproductive processes, as well as denigrating their rights through messages, images or other signs disseminated publicly; apology for scientifically contraindicated practices, with social, economic or domination purposes. [...] (PARTO DO PRINCIPIO NETWORK, 2012, p. 60)

The use of procedures without scientific recommendation may include, for example: lithotomy (horizontal position on the stretcher), amniotomy (breaking the water to speed up labor), banning the woman's movement, trichotomy (hair shaving), Kristeller (external pressure on the uterus, with the aim of reducing the expulsive period), non-use of analgesia when technically indicated, episiotomy (cut performed in the perineum to “facilitate” the baby’s exit), cesarean sections before labor in yes, among others. Add to this the threat and coercion of women who scream in pain or complain about the service, prejudice and discrimination in terms of class, race and generation, and women who use drugs or live on the street (PARTO DO PRINCIPIO, 2012)

In the case of episiotomy, the Nascer no Brasil survey (2014) revealed that it is a procedure that occurs in 53.5% of normal births, without consent and contrary to the contraindication to its reintegration, since it is not prophylactic in relation to the trauma, generating pain and discomfort in patients, in addition to potentiating future complications. Another aspect of this problem refers to the “husband’s stitch”, the suture of the episiotomy performed in a tighter way to close the vagina more and give pleasure to the husband, shaping the woman’s body to the needs of the man’s pleasure (PARTO DO PRINCIPIO, 2012)

Together, cesarean sections demonstrate the mercantile-productivist dynamics of childbirth, with Brazil leading the ranking for this resource. According to the previously mentioned research, the rate of cesarean sections in Brazil is 3 times higher than recommended - in general, 52% of deliveries are cesarean sections, in the private network it reaches 88%, when indicated by the World Health Organization (WHO) is 10 to 15%. Often performed without support, there is evidence of its relationship with increased maternal morbidity and mortality. Odent (2002), then, understands that:

the “dominant medical knowledge” repeatedly cites the risk factor [...] to justify the “wholesale medicalization” [...] it is not at all clear that [...] the “risk factor” has diminished one since many of these medical interventions actually induce new risks (p.100)

Perspective reinforced by Diniz (2009):

In Brazil, in addition to spontaneous delivery being perceived by professionals as more risky for the baby, it is also seen as more risky for the mother herself, being associated with irreversible sexual damage. Professionals practice interventions on the vagina, such as episiotomy (which is a second-degree laceration, at least) and forceps, which increase the risk of serious genital damage, and when this damage occurs, they blame the delivery itself for the damage. In this way, the iatrogenic damage is made invisible and rewritten as a “natural” damage of childbirth, associated with the physiological process and not with interventions (p.320)

Childbirth becomes a surgical and not a physiological act dictated by the space-time rules and the temporal organization of the hospital, endangering the life of the woman, and especially of the black woman, being, above all, intersectional obstetric violence, since, with based on data from the Nascer no Brasil survey, compared to white women, black postpartum women are at greater risk of having inadequate prenatal care, lack of connection to the maternity, absence of a companion, pilgrimage for childbirth and less local anesthesia for episiotomy.

Add to this the cases of abortion and post-abortion, in which obstetric violence fulfills the specific function of: being an instrument for disciplining pregnant women who refuse to obey legal and moral norms about abortion and the mandate maternity social. Thus, the Technical Norm on Humanized Care for Abortion (2005) calls for "professionals, regardless of their moral and religious precepts, to preserve an ethical posture, guaranteeing respect for women's human rights"

Contrary to the established reality, the term “obstetric violence” is rejected by professionals, seen as an offense. inappropriate connotation, does not add value and hinders the

search for humanized care in the pregnancy-delivery-puerperium continuum.” (ZOUËIN, 2019).

Here is the transformation of victims into aggressors when the corporatist narrative was created that the term aims to defame doctors and not denounce abusive conduct. Understanding reinforced by the lack of specific federal legislation against obstetric violence, enhancing impunity, the docility of female bodies to the medicalization of their pregnancies and the direction of women's subjectivities.

However, there are initiatives in the field of health that can help combat it, such as Federal Law No. 11,108/2005 (known as the Companion's Law), amending Law No. 8,080/90, to guarantee parturients the right to be present of a companion during labor, delivery and immediate postpartum, within the scope of the Unified Health System (SUS), providing that:

Art. 19-J. The health services of the Unified Health System - SUS, from their own or affiliated network, are obliged to allow the presence, with the parturient, of 1 (one) companion during the entire period of labor, delivery and immediate postpartum .

§ 1 The companion referred to in the caput of this article will be indicated by the woman in labor. [...]

§ 3 Hospitals throughout the country are obliged to keep, in a visible place on their premises, a notice informing about the right established in the caption of this article.

Right capable of providing guarantee and security to the woman, but which is violated in the following situations: restriction on the choice of companion, restriction on the companion's length of stay, restriction on the link with the institution - "only valid for the SUS" or "only plan with a private room", restriction on the type of delivery, there is understanding of the entry or stay of a companion or the stay of a companion for a fee (PARTO DO PRINCIPIO, 2012). Movement that occurs due to the woman's lack of knowledge of the right to a companion, whose choice cannot be left to the discretion of the doctor or hospital.

Other initiatives that have relevance in the confrontation, such as the Program for the Humanization of Labor and Birth, the National Humanization Policy (Humaniza SUS), the National Policy for Integral Attention to Women's Health. Both demonstrate that the humanization of childbirth, although constrained by different institutional aspects and interests, should be seen as a strategy for reaffirming women's sexual and reproductive rights, allowing dialogue with professionals about inappropriate conduct.

CONCLUSIONS

'Obstetric violence' constitutes one of the perverse forms of violence against women, strongly marked by a patriarchal-racist and capitalist society that insists on controlling the body and sexuality of women, especially black and poor women. This denial of ownership over our bodies also encompasses the right to decide about motherhood and the right to safely abort,

Therefore, overcoming the obstetric violence demarcation beyond the institutional aspect, denaturalizing and facing it, is essential in the struggle for effective public policies to humanize childbirth, with a minimum of intervention and preservation of women's protagonism. A claim that must be allied to the anti-patriarchal and anti-racist struggle in building a truly egalitarian society, eliminating the marks of slavery, patriarchy and class exploitation.

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